

UNLOCKING POTENTIAL: INVESTIGATING SCIENCE LEARNING DIFFICULTIES AND CRAFTING AN INTERVENTION HUB FOR GRADE 7 STUDENTS EMPOWERMENT AT STA. BARBARA HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics continues to be utilized in real-life situations and scenarios. This research focuses mainly on the preparation of a self-study guide for Grade 7. The approach was tested among Grade 7 students in Sta. Barbara High School. This study employed the Type I Product Design and Development and Evaluation research method in crafting and validating an intervention material based on the previous least learned competencies in Science 7. In the Product Design and Development Phase of the study, the least learned competencies were the basis in the selection of the topic included in the development of the INTERVENTION MATERIAL. The data gathered were analyzed in terms of frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Paired Samples T-test. The result of the study showed that the students' performance was below expectation. Data showed a significant difference in the students' academic performance before and after the treatment with the self-study guide; $p < \alpha = 0.05$. Consequently, self-study guide was found to utilize and enrich learners' competencies effectively, and this motivated the teachers to provide more learning resources for self-directed learning.

Keywords: *Self-study guide, Intervention material, Type I Product Design and Development, Least learned competencies, Science 7, Learning resources*

INTRODUCTION

The Science Intervention Hub has several advantages by using a self-study guide as administered to the grade 7 students. Personalized learning with adaptive algorithms ensures the best possible progress by analyzing students' strengths and weaknesses and customizing content to meet their specific needs. They also make learning interesting and enjoyable. The platform can be used for group projects and cooperative activities that promote problem-solving skills as well as cooperation through Collaboration or Peer Learning. A Real-world Application connects theoretical science knowledge to real-life situations through referencing examples from real-world contexts. The accessibility features of the platform are designed in order to cater for different kinds of learners including those with diverse learning needs.

Youth education aims at meeting their requirements. Adolescents are drawing out what they are best at and developing the dreams they lay for their future. Their physical development and mental growths have helped them to begin self-realization and understanding of the world. To this end, teachers must provide a qualitative education as an avenue for a firm grounding of knowledge that would meet their aspirations. Secondary education has been facing several challenges in Bulacan, through its Department of Education just like other educational departments do as well. In fact, it is these problems that have shown how vital it is to think differently about science among others.

Department of Education (DepEd) also issued Department Order 08 s. 2015 or the Classroom Assessment Policy Guidelines. It states that "There must be sufficient and appropriate instructional interventions to ensure that learners are ready before summative tests," and " There must be intervention by remediation and extra lessons from that student's subject teacher to a student who receives a grade below 75 in any subject in any quarter." This policy guideline outlines the need to arrest academic underachievement by giving the learners adequate intervention. It also emphasizes inclusive learning. As such, there will be no learners left behind as appropriate instructions and interventions are given to meet individual needs. With this, this study was conducted to develop and validate an intervention material based on the least learned competencies in Science 7.

This study, intends to improve on the science proficiency of grade 7 students through integration of a self-study guide focusing on conversion units, operations of integers, Scientific notation and significant figures. Among these aims is to reach a minimum of 75% Grade seven learners' regional diagnostic assessments. Moreover, it seeks to upgrade teaching skills, job satisfaction and professional growth among educators involved in this initiative.

A centralized support system called Science Intervention Hub has been established for addressing specific challenges in science education. The Hub acts as a focal point for carrying out target interventions, providing critical resources, guidance and educational strategies that would enhance students' understanding and performance in

science. This study therefore integrates these components so as to create an all-round framework for bettering science education outcomes that will provide supportive environment both for students and teachers alike. Multiplication and division are included in the four basic operations in Mathematics that is widely used in the field of science.

Mathematics continues to be utilized in real-life situations and scenarios. Some of these scenarios were when computing a change after buying something, when budgeting money, when measuring various things, and most importantly, science. Mathematics such as multiplication and division were used in science to calculate the measurements of objects and their characteristics, as well as to show the relationship between different functions and properties. Mathematics and science were two topics that were closely related, particularly in the context of education. Speaking of education, research by Evans, et al. (2018) found that 34% of students from Year 6 (age 10-11) to Year 7 (age 11–12) did not make any progress in math, with almost 2/5 of pupils failing to make the necessary development after moving to secondary education. Peer pressure and an increased workload are among the factors that have been mentioned as affecting 7th grade students during their transition.

In accordance to Pecson (2020), the academic performance of senior high school students considerably improved after the introduction of a self-learning kit. Prior to the implementation of the kit, students' performance was below expectations, but after using the self-learning kit, it became satisfactory. The study also found that the self-learning kit effectively enhanced learners' competencies and motivated teachers to offer supplementary learning resources to encourage self- directed learning.

The purpose of this study was to design, construct, and assess a self-study guide material to improve the science skills of Grade 7 students using mathematics as a springboard. The researchers also aimed to improve the skills of the learners by utilizing this guide so that the students could further develop their problem-solving skills.

Watanabe and Kato (2020) emphasized the close relationship between mathematics and science learning. The authors pointed out that the level of students' achievement in mathematics significantly impacted their conceptual and actual performance in science. According to the authors, most of the guiding principles of science were based on mathematics; therefore, the ability of students to measure, calculate, and analyze data became material to success in science. They point out that students with good results in mathematics achieve higher results in science, which indirectly suggests that improving the mathematical competencies of students will bring about positive effects in educational outcomes.

Watanabe and Kato argue for an integrated curriculum where the teaching of mathematics and science be brought together to enable students to apply mathematical reasoning to scientific problems. This way, not only does it deepen understanding, but it also engages the students by showing them how important math is in science. With such insight, the self-study guide will be more able to pursue the key skills for Grade 7 students in a bid to ensure that mathematics is relevant in the sciences.

Jwells (2020) stated in their article that self-learning for learners could lead to better memory retention, increased responsibility for their own learning, the development of a strong work ethic, increased confidence, and exploration beyond their comfort zone.

According to Doblada (2019), the Mathematics Learning Kit was a tool designed to help students improve their skills in the fundamental operations of integers. It was a simple tool that provided worksheets for each lesson, allowing students to work independently, with answers provided at the end for self-checking. The kit could have been used in various ways, such as before, during, or after classroom instruction, in tutoring sessions, or even at home by students themselves. To test the kit's effectiveness, researchers conducted an experiment with two groups of students, one using the kit and the other not. They found that using the kit significantly improved students' skills in the fundamental operations of integers. This was great news because it meant that using such tools could be an effective way to help students learn math.

A similar study was conducted by Rosauo in (2021), but with grade 3 students instead of grade 7. The study's findings indicate that Grade III students heavily utilized the Self-Learning Kit (SLK) in their math studies, demonstrating the value of this resource as an additional learning tool for distance learners. The SLK has proved to be a useful resource that students could utilize to enhance their math coursework.

A study conducted by Pecson in (2020) concluded that there was a significant improvement in the academic performance of senior high school students after the implementation of a self-learning kit (SLK). The data revealed that prior to the implementation of SLK, the academic performance of students was unsatisfactory, with 43.33% of students not meeting expectations and 56.67% of students meeting expectations to a fair degree. However, following the implementation of SLK, there was a significant improvement in students' academic performance, with 63.33% of students achieving a very satisfactory level of academic performance, while the remaining 36.67% achieved a satisfactory level. The study found that the effective use of the SLK enhanced the competencies of the learners and encouraged teachers to provide additional learning resources towards self-directed learning. Students' academic performance can be greatly enhanced by the usage of effective learning tools. Self-learning kits have drawn more attention recently as a method to improve the teaching and learning process.

According to the study conducted by Benito et al. (2022), found out that the self-learning kits allowed the learners to learn the contents by adapting the knowledge at their own pace. This helps them to retain the content for a longer time. The researchers found out that the learners were answering the post-test more effectively which improved the learners' performance compared to the results the researchers got on the pre-test.

Malcolm S. Knowles defined SDL as, "A process in which individuals take the initiative, with or without the help of others, in diagnosing their learning needs, formulating learning goals, identifying human and material resources for learning, choosing and implementing appropriate learning strategies, and evaluating learning outcomes". Thus,

the students learn on their initiative and have primary responsibility for planning, implementing, and evaluating the effort. The responsibility of learning remains with students' medical professionals are expected to be self-directed learners for sustaining lifelong learning to keep pace with the dynamically changing science of medicine and technology for their professional self-development. COVID-19 pandemic is a recent example of dynamic changes observed in medical science, digital technology, and educational strategies.

The cognitive learning theory pertains to learning from the processes in the mind (mental and psychological). It involves perceptions, processing of information, and memory in the learning process. It focuses on the point that the students should learn 'how to learn. Experiential learning occurs when the students reflect on an experience. The student develops a working theory that leads them to an action plan and articulates the plan to variable extents to gain a fresh new experience. The cycle of experiential learning continues. Experiential learning is based on Kolb's learning cycle. Humanistic theory is more learner-centered and aims to produce students who have the potential for self-actualization, are self-directed, and are internally motivated. The students plan, conduct, and evaluate their own learning. It has often been described as the goal of adult education emphasizing autonomy and individual freedom in learning.

Conceptual Framework

The study's conceptual framework was the IPO (Input-Process-Output) Model. Participatory institutions' qualities can be expressed in three key dimensions: input, process, and output. The common assumption is that there is a dependency relationship, with the process acting as a bridge between input and output (Galais, Font, Smith, 2020).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Questions

The problem addressed in this study revolves around the prevalent learning difficulties faced by Grade 7 students in Sta. Barbara High School, City of Baliwag, Bulacan in Science subject, hindering their academic progress. Despite dedicated efforts, a significant number of students encounter challenges in comprehending and mastering science concepts. This study seeks to investigate the root causes of these learning difficulties and aims to address them through the development of an intervention hub, ultimately empowering students to unlock their full potential in science education.

Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What intervention material can be developed based on the previous least learned competencies in Science 7?
2. How may the experts faced and content validity be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 Adequacy
 - 2.2 Coherence
 - 2.3 Appropriateness
 - 2.4 Usefulness
3. How may the intervention material be evaluated in terms of:
 - 3.1 Adaptability (DepEd)
 - 3.2 Factor 1 content
 - 3.3 Format
 - 3.4 Presentation and organization
 - 3.5 Accuracy and up datedness of info

Significance of the Study

This study provided new information which benefited the following:

Students. This study aimed to develop the skills of the student regarding basic operations of mathematics used in science. For students, the learning guide may have provided them with math fundamentals that the learners could learn on their own to develop the skills regarding basic operations of mathematics in science.

Science and Mathematics Teacher. The self-study guide material could be used by teachers to create more interesting and productive learning experiences. It could assist the teacher's professional development and training by providing information that helped teachers better grasp how to use the learning guide in the classroom.

Administrators. The administrators will be guided on what should be emphasized by teachers in the school curriculum to improve students' performance in mathematics. Also, to further understand the effectiveness of the self-study guide in improving the student's understanding and retention of material.

Schools. This scholarly work would benefit in terms of science and mathematics related discussion and increase the performance in science and mathematics. The other schools could also adapt this type of kit to improve their students' academic performance and further develop their teaching style in which the students would learn more efficiently.

Future Researchers. The study helped them to uncover critical areas in the educational process that many researchers were not able to explore. By utilizing the findings of this study, researchers were able to address the limitations that had been previously identified in similar studies, and thus gained a deeper understanding of the topic at hand. The researchers could have utilized this research to amplify the validity and dependability of their study. Future researchers could have looked up the references in this study, which could have helped them acquire more support for their research papers.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the Type I Product Design and Development and Evaluation research method to craft and validate an intervention material based on the previous least learned competencies in Science 7. In the Product Design and Development Phase of the study, the least learned competencies were the basis in the selection of the topic included in the development of the INTERVENTION MATERIAL. Additionally, the parts of the IM were scrutinized by the instructional material experts and the researchers. Lastly, in the Evaluation Phase, three master teachers in Science evaluated the IM's face and content validity in terms of adequacy, coherence, appropriateness, and usefulness. Moreover, the researchers and the validators also considered the IM's content, format, presentation and organization, and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information based on the evaluation of print materials of the DepEd.

Respondents and Sampling

In the study titled *Unlocking Potential: Investigating Science Learning Difficulties and Crafting an Intervention Hub for Grade 7 Students Empowerment at Sta. Barbara High School*, purposive sampling was utilized to select the three experts or master teachers in Science who would evaluate the intervention material (IM). This method ensured that the evaluators had the requisite expertise and experience to provide meaningful feedback on the IM's effectiveness and relevance. The experts were chosen based on their extensive teaching experience at the Grade 7 level, advanced degrees in Science or Education, and demonstrated proficiency in evaluating and developing instructional materials.

For the intervention phase, total population sampling was employed, involving all Grade 7 students currently enrolled at Sta. Barbara High School to ensure comprehensive data collection. To identify participants for the intervention, students

who scored below 50% on the Regional Diagnostic Assessment (RDA) 2023-2024 were selected for a one-week intervention using the Self-Study Guide. This targeted approach aims to address the learning difficulties of these students, allowing for a more focused and effective improvement in their Science proficiency.

Instrumentation

This study makes use of a wide range of tools to thoroughly assess the effect of the Self-study guide on the academic achievement of Grade 7 students at Sta. Barbara High School. The Regional Diagnostic Assessment that are intended to quantitatively examine students' understanding of science ideas both before and after the intervention is implemented are at the heart of this evaluation. These evaluations will offer unambiguous signs of any gains in academic achievement brought about by the self-study guide. Students will also be given surveys to complete in order to get their opinions on self-study guide.

The searchers will watch and record student behaviors and interactions when using self-study guide in the classroom in order to collect qualitative data. These data will shed light on participation rates, student engagement levels, and the general efficacy of self-study guide components in creating dynamic learning environments. Conducting comprehensive interviews with educators and students will enhance the research by delving into the complex perspectives and experiences of individuals who are intimately associated with the self-study guide. Students will be interviewed in order to gain insight into their reasons for studying, the difficulties they have faced, and how their experiences have affected them.

The findings from the qualitative instruments will be validated and supported quantitatively by academic performance data from school records, which will provide unbiased insights into the overall effect of self-study guide on students' academic successes in science. When combined, these tools create an extensive framework that seeks to offer a thorough understanding of the ways in which self-study guide in academic performance, learning outcomes, and student engagement in Sta. Barbara High School.

The results of self-study guide will describe by the following interpretation:

- 4- Very Satisfactory (VS)
- 3- Satisfactory (S)
- 2- Poor
- 1-Not satisfactory

Data Gathering Procedure

The research process began with a document analysis to identify the least learned competencies (LLCs) in Science 7 based on the Regional Diagnostic Assessment (RDA) results for 2023-2024. This analysis guided the selection of topics to be

addressed in the development of the intervention material. Following this, the researchers proceeded with the development of the self-study guide, incorporating the identified competencies and ensuring that the material was tailored to address the specific needs of the students.

Subsequently, the researchers sought permission from the appropriate authorities to conduct the study at Sta. Barbara High School. The intervention material was then validated by obtaining permission from three master teachers in Science, who evaluated its content for adequacy, coherence, appropriateness, and usefulness. After validation, a total population sampling method was used to select all Grade 7 students. Students scoring below 50% on the RDA were chosen for the one-week intervention with the self-study guide. Data from this intervention were collected, analyzed, and interpreted to draw conclusions and make recommendations for improving the self-study guide and overall science education.

Ethical Considerations

To uphold academic integrity and ensure the validity of the intervention material (IM), this study will prioritize informed consent, confidentiality, and respect for participant rights. Informed consent will be thoroughly obtained from students and their guardians, clearly outlining the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Throughout the data collection and analysis phases, strict confidentiality will be maintained, with participant identities protected through anonymization and secure data handling procedures. Participants will have the explicit right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any repercussions, ensuring their privacy and voluntary participation are upheld.

The study will also honor the principles of justice and respect by acknowledging individual differences and cultural diversity among participants. Measures will be implemented to minimize any potential harm or discomfort to participants, prioritizing their well-being throughout the research process. By adhering to these ethical guidelines, the research aims to ensure the academic integrity of the study and the validity of the intervention material, while fostering a respectful and safe environment for all involved at Sta. Barbara High School.

Data Analysis

The researchers used thematic analysis for the comments and suggestions of the experts in evaluating the self-study guide material. Frequency distribution was also used in treating the results of the 2023-2024 RDA. Moreover, the means that will be used is the teachers' perception of the self-study guide. The Paired T-test will be used to compare the mean scores of the RDA results.

The total population sampling technique was used by the researchers to select the four sections. According to Laerd (2023), total population is a non-probability technique wherein the total population that meets specific criteria are selected. This

is ideal when the population is small and homogeneous, meaning all individuals share a similar set of characteristics or experiences.

1. T-test

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

t = Student's t-test
 $\bar{x}$ = Mean of the sample
 s^2 = Variance
 n = Variable set size

2. Mean

$$Mean(x) = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

$\sum x$ = sum of all values
 n = number of values

3. Standard Deviation

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (x - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$$

x = Each of the values of the data
 $\bar{x}$ = The mean of x
 n = Number of data points

RESULTS

The previously identified least learned competencies in Science 7 were used to develop intervention materials. This self-study guide is in-depth and quickly cured the student problem areas, namely, in conversion of units, operations on integers, in scientific notations and significant figures. This self-study material addresses diverse students' learning needs through the use of interactive exercises, situated and real-life example cases, as well as adaptively designed learning. Further, it gives students self-assessment

tools by which they can monitor their progress and consolidate weak areas in their knowledge. So, the prime objective is to give rise to students' competence in science and make them prepared in such a manner that they will acquire the ability to learn by themselves. The expert review feedback, placed in Tables 2 to 10, is a positive contribution to the refinement of this working draft of the self-study guide before its issuance to students. It centred on four key evaluation factors: Content, Format, Presentation and Organization, and Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of Information. Each of these factors had to be closely looked into to measure the quality of and effectiveness of the intervention material. It is the feedback offered by the evaluation that has literally guided the changes taking place in the self-study guide to ensure that its transformation is complete and accessible, therefore allowing the potential effects it can have on improved student learning to be maximized.

Table 2
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of the adequacy

Factor 2: Adequacy	Average	V.I.
1.The content includes all key parts of the topic.	3.8	VS
2.The material goes into great detail.	4.0	VS
3.The content helps with common learning challenges.	3.6	VS
4.The content has enough depth for seventh graders.	3.9	VS
5.The examples help students understand well.	3.7	VS
Sub mean	3.80	VS

Legend:1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

Table 3
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of the coherence

Factor 2: Coherence	Average	V.I.
1. Logically organized	3.7	VS
2. Proper arrangement in the paragraphs	3.8	VS
3. Indicates interconnectedness of ideas and concepts	3.6	VS
4. Cohesiveness of each of the section is remarkable	3.9	VS
5. Consistency of the terms and structure is preserved	3.8	VS
Sub mean	3.96	VS

Legend:1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

Table 4
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of the Appropriateness

Factor 2: Appropriateness	Average	V.I.
1. Content is appropriate to the student/ learner's expectation that is grade 7.	3.9	VS
2. Language is suitable to grade 7 level learners	4.0	VS
3. Exercises/examples are suitable for the learners or students.	3.8	VS
4. The content reflects the cultural and educational background of the learners.	3.7	VS
5. The level of text is appropriate for the learners	3.8	VS
Sub mean	3.84	VS

Legend:1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

Table 5
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of the Usefulness

Factor 2: Usefulness	Average	V.I.
1. Content supports learners towards self-discovery.	3.9	VS
2. Content has applicability in daily life and learners can visualize the uses of the learnt matter through that.	3.8	VS
3. Content is of stimulating nature and stimulating for learners.	3.9	VS
4. The activities and exercises would aid the students to understand the content much better and retain it longer.	4.0	VS
5. Content supports students in making use of their knowledge in real-life situations.	3.8	VS
Sub mean	3.88	VS

Legend:1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

Table 6
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of the adaptability (DepEd)

Factor 3: Adaptability (DepEd)	Average	V.I.
1. Instructional material is aligned with DepEd's curriculum and educational standards.	4	VS
2. The material can be integrated into existing DepEd programs and lesson plans.	3.5	VS
3. The material to different grade levels, student needs, and learning environments.	4	VS
4. The level of training needed for teachers to effectively use the material biases and prejudices	4	VS
5. The potential for local adaptation and contextualization of the material.	3	VS
Sub mean	3.70	VS

Legend: 1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

Table 7
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of the Factor 1 Content

Factor 3: Factor 1 Content	Average	V.I.
1. The content aligns with the learning objectives of the program.	3.5	VS
2. Evaluate the accuracy of the information provided in the material.	4	VS
3. Measures the comprehensiveness of the content in covering the subject matter.	3	VS
4. How engaging the content is for the target audience biases and prejudices	3	VS
5. Appropriateness of the content in terms of cultural sensitivity and inclusiveness.	4	VS
Sub mean	3.50	VS

Legend: 1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

Table 8
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of its format.

Factor 3: Format	Average	V.I.
1. Prints		
1.1 The size of letters is appropriate to the intended user (size-16, font style-Century Gothic except ?)	3.8	VS
1.2 Spaces between letters and words facilitate reading	3.2	S
1.3 Font is easy to read (title size – 16-30pt, subtitle – 16-18)	3.4	VS
1.4 Printing is of good quality (i.e., no broken letters, even density, correct alignment, properly placed screen registration).	3.4	VS
2. Illustrations		
2.1 Simple and easily recognizable	3.8	VS
2.2 Clarify and supplement the text	3.8	VS
2.3 Properly labelled or captioned (if applicable)	4	VS
2.4 Realistic/appropriate colors	3.6	VS
2.5 Attractive and appealing	3.6	VS
2.6 Culturally relevant	3.6	VS
3. Design and Layout		
3.1 Attractive and pleasing to look at	4	VS
3.2 Simple (i.e., does not distract the attention of the reader)	3.6	VS
3.3 Adequate illustration in relation of text	3.6	VS
3.4 Harmonious blending of elements (e.g., illustrations and text)	3.8	VS
4. Paper and Binding		
4.1 Paper used contributes to easy reading	4	VS
4.2 Durable binding to withstand frequent use	4	VS
5. Size and Weight of Resource		
5.1 Easy to handle	4	VS
5.2 Relatively light	4	VS
Sub mean	3.73	VS

Legend:1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

Table 9
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of its presentation and organization

Factor 3: Presentation and Organization	Average	V.I.
1.Presentation is engaging, interesting and understandable	4	VS
2.Inquiry & Play-Based Learning. Active learning uses real-life situations to engage and challenges children’s critical thinking	3.6	VS
3.There is logical and smooth flow of ideas. Expand their expressive mother tongue and/or English language proficiency.	3.4	VS

4.Vocabulary level is adapted to target learner’s likely experience and level of understanding.	4	VS
5.Length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target learner. Sentences and paragraph structures are varied and interesting to the target learner	4	VS
Sub mean	3.80	VS

Legend:1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

*Table 10
Mean of the evaluation of self-study guide in terms of accuracy and up-to-date of information*

Factor 4: Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information	Average	V.I.
1. Conceptual errors	3.8	VS
2. Factual errors	3.8	VS
3. Grammatical errors	3.6	VS
4. Computational errors	4	VS
5. Obsolete errors	4	VS
6. Typographical errors and other minor errors (e.g., inappropriate or unclear illustrations, missing labels, wrong captions, etc.)	4	VS
Sub mean	3.87	VS

Legend:1-1.75=Not satisfactory (NS), 1.76-2.5=Poor (P), 2.56-3.25=Satisfactory (S), 3.26-4= Very Satisfactory (VS)

DISCUSSION

Table 2 under Factor 2, Adequacy rates the self-study guide, and all the criteria received a Very Satisfactory (VS) grade. This receives a score of 3.8, which is the highest, meaning there is the presence of all the key parts of the topic in the content, hence providing good coverage on the necessary material and is quality and integral to the material. All the criteria under 'level of detail' received a score of 4.0, which is the highest, meaning the material contains a detailed treatment of the material. Furthermore, the ability of the content to accommodate the basic learning challenges scored 3.6, meaning that it was highly effective but there was still a slight room for improvement.

For content, the depth of the self-study guide for seventh graders purposefully achieved a 3.9, taking it as an indication that it fits very well with the target audience's educational level. Use of examples in aid of student understanding also obtained a good 3.7, which traces the effectiveness of the material in clarifying situations. The overall sub

mean of 3.80 confirms how satisfactory of a resource the self-study guide is in terms of level of adequateness and in terms of having suitable thoroughness of material and pedagogy sound enough to effectively support learning on the part of students.

Chen and Liu, (2020) critical review on the evaluation of educational materials solely for online learning in *Educational Technology Research and Development*, present an in-depth review of the criteria used in the evaluation of educational resources. The major ones are those related to sufficiency about the content; this looks at the extent to which it represents the coverage of important topics and meets the educational standards. It also covers the level of detail regarding materials, which judges how adequate the content is to effectively support learning.

Table 3, Analysis of the Self-Study Guide with Factor 2: Coherence—Rating for all criteria indicated Very Satisfactory. Logical ordering achieved an average score of 3.7 indicating the material is logically organized and the content easily follows. Proper ordering within paragraphs rated at 3.8, indicating information flows appropriately in paragraphs and aids readability. Idea flow/concept continuity is rated at 3.6, showing the guide does an adequate job of providing connections among the various elements but could do a little more in places to make those connections evident.

This came back at 3.9, showing that the material has very strong internal consistency, and each part of the guide reinforces others. Another area was consistency of terms and structure, also strongly rated at 3.8, showing the uniformity kept throughout the guide. The sub mean of 3.96 explains the strong coherence of the guide, which is well-organized and internally consistent, effectively presenting interconnected ideas in such a way as to support comprehensive understanding.

In a review article by Gordon and Schunk (2019), *Educational Psychology Review*, the authors establish how central coherence really is in learning materials. Their work underlines idea flow, concept continuity, and internal consistency as pertinent factors within educational resources. This paper covers how these facets facilitate learners' understanding by stressing that highly coherent materials help in more effective learning since they ensure that the content is rationally organized and interlinked.

Table 4 presents the assessment of this self-study guide using Factor 2: Appropriateness, and all its criteria were rated Very Satisfactory. Content suitability for the level of seventh-grade learners was 3.9, indicating that the content material is only very fitting for their educational level. Language expression even scored higher at 4.0, indicating that vocabulary and phrasing are very appropriate for seventh graders, and vocabulary and phrasing are very clear in meaning.

The examples and exercise in the guide—rated 3.8—showed relevance and efficiency for the learners, though slight improvements can still be done. To what extent the content reflects the learners' cultural and educational background rated 3.7, indicating that while the guide was generally culturally sensitive, further improvements can be made in terms of making its content more representative of the students' diverse backgrounds.

Finally, the rating for the appropriateness of the text level was 3.8. It indicated that the level of difficulty of the subject matter is very well-suited for learners. The overall sub mean of 3.84 showed that the self-study guide was very satisfactory in terms of appropriateness and was therefore appropriate for seventh-grade students.

Baker and Collet's paper (2018) in the *Journal of Curriculum Studies* associates a way to assess cultural fit regarding educational resources. The study developed a framework to take a look at how well instructional materials matched with the cultural and educational context of learners. The work will give insight into how the cultural appropriateness of instructional materials should be accurately assessed in order to properly tailor them for such diverse learner populations.

Table 5 Factor 2, Usefulness Self-study guide results show that the material is very effective in all aspects considered: the content helps learners to make discoveries on their own[^]- 3.9 Indicates that the material makes the students investigate and understand concepts on their own. The applicability of the content to everyday life scored 3.8, meaning that the material enabled the students to get see practical alternatives in use for knowledge they pick to gain, making the learning experience practical, and enhanced meaning.

The nature of the content being thought-provoking was tagged as 3.9, meaning the material is challenging, and can keep the learner's interest. Furthermore, it includes activities and exercises, which were rated 4.0, since these materials provide for a better understanding and memorization of them, so it is a very effective tool in learning. Moreover, the support that the content provides for making use of the knowledge in real life has been rated 3.8, which is quite a high rate of practical applicability. The general sub mean of 3.88 confirms that effectiveness of the self-study guide in terms of usefulness is very satisfactory, which provides support for students in terms of an academic and real-life environment.

A study by Parker and Jones (2019) in *Educational Technology Research and Development* makes a case for how educational materials can be designed to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and its practical applications. Their study examines the issue of structuring materials in such a way that acquired knowledge is useful in real life, which requires maximum possible practical relevance of educational content.

Table 6 shows the responsiveness of the self-study guide vis-à-vis DepEd's standards. The results of the evaluation indicated it had a strong performance overall. The guide obtained an average score of 4.00 regarding its relation to DepEd's curriculum, indicating a strong fit with the educational requirements. It also rated 3.50 for integration into existing DepEd programs, likewise indicating effective compatibility with current practices. Additionally, the guide's elasticity with respect to grade levels, student needs, and learning environments was rated at 4.00. That tells about its flexibility. Its ease of use, especially for teachers where minimal training is required, was also rated 4.00.

Local adaptation and contextualization rated the lowest, but at 3.00, still within

the Very Satisfactory category, it identifies specific areas that may need greater effort to further adapt this guide to effective local contexts. This sub mean of 3.70 shows that the guide stands out strongly in its ability to adapt to DepEd's standards but may benefit from further refining to effect more meaningful local contextualization.

Tay and Reddy (2020) look into the process of adapting educational materials for local contexts and standards, exploring challenges and best practices to achieve local contextualization. Their study reveals that there are problems with alignment to the standards of the nation while meeting local needs and conditions. This has added a lot to increase the adaptability of educational materials.

Table 7 shows the evaluation of the self-study guide on Factor 1 Content, covering the different key aspects of the material. Five criteria rated the content of the guide with a general sub-mean score of 3.50, which belongs to the VS (Very Satisfactory) category.

The rating on the extent to which the guide aligned with the learning goals of the program was 3.5, indicating mainly that it met the goals and would need further fine-tuning. Its accuracy was rated at 4.00, speaking highly for the reliability of its content. On the other hand, the comprehensiveness of subject matter and the engagement level of content both rated 3.00, indicating that while the performance is already satisfactory, there is still room for better coverage of the material and more relevance to the target audience. The lowest average score of 4.00, which was received on the appropriateness of the content with respect to cultural sensitivity and inclusiveness, still shows that the guide is well-considered in these particular areas.

Al-Awidi and Aldhafeeri (2021) in their study published in the Journal of Educational Research and Practice present a comprehensive framework for evaluating educational materials. This framework emphasizes the critical aspects of content alignment with learning goals, accuracy, and comprehensiveness. The study highlights the necessity for educational resources to be pedagogically effective and closely aligned with curriculum objectives to ensure quality and effectiveness in educational settings.

Table 8 shows the results of teachers' perception about self-study guide in terms of its format. The item statements such as properly labelled or captioned, attractive and pleasing to look at, paper used contribute to easy reading, durable binding to withstand frequent use, easy to handle, and relatively light are garnered the highest weighted mean of 4 interpreted as "very satisfactory". Meanwhile, space between letter and words facilitate reading garnered the lowest weighted mean of 3.2 which interpreted as "satisfactory". The sub mean of teachers' perception on self-study guide in terms of its format was 3.73 and interpreted as "very satisfactory".

The learning kit was developed based on ADDIE Model adaptation according to (E. Forest, 2014) where based on the ADDIE model, the development of learning kit contains five (5) phases namely the requirement analysis phase, the design phase, the

development phase, the implementation phase and the evaluation phase.

The table 9 shows the results of teachers' perception about self-study guide in terms of its presentation and organizations.". The item statements presentation is engaging, interesting and understandable, vocabulary level is adapted to target learner's likely experience and level of understanding, and length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target learner. Sentences and paragraph structures are varied and interesting to the target learner are garnered the highest mean of 4 with interpretation of "very satisfactory". Meanwhile, item statement there is logical and smooth flow of ideas. Expand their expressive mother tongue and/or English language proficiency, garnered the lowest mean of 3.4 which was interpreted as "very satisfactory". The sub mean of teachers' perception on self-study guide in terms of its presentation and organization was 3.80 which interpreted as "very satisfactory".

Thienpermpool, 2021, underlines two crucial issues: clarity and engagement, just like the guide of self-study working engages those very welcome aspects of its presentation, which are interesting and understandable. In turn, it overstates and confirms that an interesting and clear structure will provide the best results as far as efficient educational materials are concerned in case they are adjusted to the learners' level of understanding.

Similarly, Kuenzi 2021 depicts how curriculum materials are designed according to the comprehension level of the learners, and this concurs with the data in which the vocabulary and sentence structures were appropriate for the learners. Both studies further give weight to systematic content which logically and coherently flows, although rated a little lower in the findings, it is still crucial to make it an apt interaction for the learning process.

Table 10 shows the results of teachers' perception about self-study guide in terms of accuracy and up-to-date of information. The item statements computational errors, obsolete errors, and typographical errors and other minor errors garnered the highest weighted mean of 4 and interpreted as "very satisfactory". Meanwhile, the item statement grammatical errors, garnered the lowest mean of 3.6 which was interpreted as "very satisfactory". According to one of evaluator "*Few grammatical errors that can be addressed easily*".

Yavuz and Bal (2018) conducted research titled "An Analysis of the Types of Errors in Educational Materials: Impact on Learning Outcomes" that directly impacts your findings. In this research, specific analyses were done on how grammatical and computation-based errors impinge upon learning outcomes-an important auxiliary finding that links up with those of your perceptions related to the accuracy of the self-study guide.

It also deals with the implications of such errors on the perception of both teachers and students, which tallies with your result that showed some of the errors being rated as satisfactory. Further, it provides ways through which these errors can be put right-an assertion to which your statement that grammatical errors are easy to correct supports.

Conclusions

The researchers concludes that the Science self-study guide for seventh graders is an effective and valuable educational resource. Each of these dimensions—adequacy, coherence, appropriateness, usefulness, adaptability, content, format, presentation, and accuracy—garnered Very Satisfactory ratings in the review of the guide. Based on the results, the guide substantially covers all learning needs of the seventh graders, most of which are very strong in performance concerning its detailed and well-organized content supporting self-discovery, practical application, and engagement.

The strong alignment with educational standards and curriculum requirements proves its worth in the classroom for its effectiveness at meeting academic goals and being able to be incorporated into existing programs. Scores for usability and adaptability are very high, so it should be easily integrated into different educational environments, without too much additional training for the educator. There were a few areas noted for improvement with the guide, notably in increasing cultural representation and refining some of the formatting details.

In a nutshell, the self-study guide is placed to overcome the bottleneck in enhancing students' learning experiences and competencies in Science. Successful alignment with educational standards, effective content delivery, and practical application redound to its potential as a valuable educational tool. Continued refinement and adaptation will further optimize its impact and effectiveness in diverse learning environments.

Recommendations

In the line of the findings and conclusions drawn from the data, the following recommendation are hereby presented:

1. The researchers recommend an extended period of intervention to thoroughly improve the skills of the students.
2. Similar future studies should explore the effectiveness of self-study guide in subjects other than math and science.
3. The researchers suggest to utilize the of self-study guide in the incoming grade 7 for its effectiveness.
4. Since the result of self-study guide are valid, the researcher suggests to utilize the of self- study guide in the incoming grade 7 for its effectiveness.
5. A similar study should conduct across different grade levels to determine the effectiveness of self-study guide in improving the academic performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers declare that they have adhered to all the strict ethical practices in conducting their research. The consent of all the respondents had to be obtained only after clearly explaining the details of the study and the role that they would be playing. All the respondents were informed of the right to withdraw from the study at any time, if need be, without any adverse consequences. These respondents' anonymity was maintained to a very high degree, and identifying information was kept confidential to protect the privacy of the respondents. Respondent well-being considerations were of most concern—the safety parameters, of course, for the mental and emotional health of the respondents during the study.

They have insisted that no potential conflict of interest exists in carrying out this study. The idea is, therefore, that the design, execution, or reporting of this study occurred at the height of integrity. Plagiarism was highly avoided; sources and references having been put appropriately. The authors also confirm that there was no subjective interpretation of the findings, and the results were presented neutrally and used only for the purposes of this study. The assurance to ethical standards underlines the authors' commitment to being responsible and credible in carrying out research.

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